

CALCULATIONS OF THE SPATIAL COHERENCE AND ARRAY NOISE GAIN OF WIND-GENERATED NOISE

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Abstract

A model of wind-generated ambient acoustic noise in the ocean will be described, and some of its applications will be illustrated. Using a normal mode representation of the noise field, the relative noise intensity as a function of depth and the spatial coherence between any two points in the medium can be calculated. In this form, the model is particularly applicable to shallow water. Examples will be given of calculated intensity vs. depth and vertical and horizontal coherence for several sets of environmental conditions. The model can be used to calculate array noise gain and, combined with a signal field model, array gain. Examples of signal to noise level and array noise gain calculations will be presented.

1. Introduction

The problem of modeling the characteristics of wind-generated noise in the ocean can be divided into two parts: (1) determining the nature and properties of the sources, and (2) calculating how the sound field generated by the sources is propagated to the receivers. We have developed a model which addresses the second part of the problem. The model is based on wave theory, not ray theory, and enables the calculation of the level and spatial coherence of the noise.

2. The Model

The model geometry is shown in Figure 1. The figure illustrates a simple case of a water layer with density ρ_1 and depth-dependent sound-speed $C_1(z)$ overlying a semi-infinite bottom with density ρ_2 and depth-dependent sound speed $C_2(z)$. Although not indicated in the figure, absorption in the water and the bottom can be included, as can attenuation (but not loss of coherence) due to surface and bottom roughness, and a layered bottom with finite rigidity. The sources are assumed to be monopoles distributed continuously over a plane slightly below the surface and parallel to it. In the calculations to follow,

the sources are taken to be uncorrelated and a normal mode representation of the noise field is used. Since the source levels are left arbitrary, only relative intensity as a function of depth can be calculated. To obtain absolute noise levels, source levels obtained either from theory or measurements can be included. The spatial coherence, which is a normalized quantity, can be calculated between any two points in the medium. In some of the examples shown below, a transmission loss model², based on the same normal mode representation of the signal field, is used.

3. Results

In the following, we illustrate the effects of sound-speed profile and bottom type on relative wind-noise level, spatial coherence, transmission loss, relative signal-to-noise level, and array noise gain. Unless otherwise noted, the frequency is 400 Hz. To calculate the effect of sound-speed profile, we chose the three generic profiles shown in Figure 2, an isovelocity, an upward refracting, and a downward refracting profile. Two bottom types were used in the calculations, a high-loss bottom (silt) and a low-loss bottom (fine sand). Figures 3(a), (b), and (c) show the relative noise level vs. depth for all three profiles and both bottom types. The results for the isovelocity profile [3(a)] and the downward refracting profile [3(b)] are nearly identical. For the high-loss bottom the level decreases with depth; the level near the surface is about 10 dB higher than at the bottom. For the low-loss bottom the level is independent of depth. The level over the low-loss bottom is from 7 to 20 dB higher than the level over the high-loss bottom. For the upward refracting profile [3(c)], the noise level is higher in the upper part of the water column than the lower. The difference is only about 4 dB for the low-loss bottom, but is over 12 dB for the high-loss bottom. Interestingly, the levels are nearly the same in the sound channel. This is explained by the fact that the lower order modes (corresponding to rays trapped in the channel) do not interact with the bottom and, therefore, are only slightly attenuated. Hence these modes, which dominate the noise field in the channel, are hardly affected by the change in properties of the bottom. Comparing the upward refracting profile to the others, it is seen that the levels of the former are higher at all depths and for both bottom types.

The signal level, like the noise level, is dependent on depth, frequency, and environment.

In addition, it depends on source depth and the distance between the source and receiver. Figure 4 shows the transmission loss for a source at mid-depth and frequency of 400 Hz as a function of depth for the three sound-speed profiles over the high-loss bottom. The downward refracting profile, which produces more interaction with the bottom, shows significant departure from the others in the upper part of the water column. In the lower half of the water column, the difference is much smaller. The transmission loss vs. depth curves over the low-loss bottom (not shown) vary little with sound-speed profile, but their levels are higher, as expected.

Figures 5(a), (b), (c), and (d) show plots of horizontal noise coherence vs. receiver separation at 400 Hz for both the upward and the downward refracting profiles over both the high-loss and low-loss bottoms. Two receiver depths are shown, shallow (15 m) and deep (90 m). From the point of view of array performance, the position of the first null of the coherence and its envelope are of greatest importance. Thus, the downward refracting profile over the high-loss bottom [5(a)] shows the most significant depth dependence. The other cases show little if any difference with depth. Further, there is little profile dependence over the low-loss bottom [5(c), (d)]. In contrast there are very significant differences between the upward and downward refracting profiles over the high-loss bottom [5(a), (b)], particularly in the position of the first null.

The vertical coherence shows much greater sensitivity to profile and bottom type. An example of vertical coherence is shown in Figure 6.

The noise gain of an array can be calculated from the spatial coherence. We have performed the calculations for unshaded horizontal arrays of 7, 13, and 25 elements uniformly spaced at half wavelength intervals at 400 Hz. The results for the downward and upward refracting profiles are shown in Figures 7(a) and (b). For reference we have also shown the line $10 \log N$, where N is the number of elements. We note from the figures that the noise gain is less than $10 \log N$ in all cases except the downward refracting profile over the high-loss bottom (Since the noise gain is subtracted from the signal gain to give the array gain, lower noise gain implies higher array gain.) The high-loss bottom also exhibits depth dependence of the noise gain for both profiles.

To test the performance of an array at a frequency other than the design frequency, the same array configurations shown in the previous figures (with half-wavelength spacings at 400 Hz) were used to calculate the noise gain down to an octave lower. In all cases the noise gain increased linearly as the frequency decreased. At 200 Hz, the noise gain was 3 dB higher than at 400 Hz.

The relative signal to noise ratio (the negative of the sum of the transmission loss and the relative noise level) is shown in Figures 8(a), (b), and (c) for a single omni-directional receiver. The examples shown were computed for a source at mid-depth at a range of 10 km from the receivers. The results show that in all cases, the relative signal to noise ratio is greatest in the lower half of the water column. The reason for this is the decrease in noise level with depth, as seen in Figures 3(a), (b), and (c), coupled with the nearly constant or increasing signal level with depth, shown in Figure 4.

4. Summary

We have presented a model which can be used to calculate the spatial properties of the acoustic field generated in the ocean by the action of wind at the surface. Examples of relative noise level and spatial coherence for relatively complex shallow water environments have been given. The model has been applied to predictions of the noise gain of horizontal arrays and, combined with a signal field model, the relative signal to noise ratio.

Acknowledgement

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References

1. W. A. Kuperman and F. Ingenito, J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 67, 1988-1996 (1980).
2. J. F. Miller and S. N. Wolf, Naval Research Laboratory Report 8429, August 27, 1980.

Figure 1 - Model geometry

Figure 2 - The three generic sound-speed profiles used in this study. An isovelocity profile A, a downward refracting profile B, and an upward refracting profile C.

Figure 3 - The relative noise level vs. depth for both bottom types and (a) the isovelocity profile, (b) the downward refracting profile, and (c) the upward refracting profile.

Figure 4 - Transmission loss vs. depth for all three sound-speed profiles over the high-loss (silt) bottom. The source was at mid-depth and the source-receiver separation was 10 km.

5(b)

5(a)

5(c)

5(d)

Figure 5 - Horizontal wind-noise coherence vs. receiver separation D for (a) the downward refracting profile over the high-loss bottom, (b) the upward refracting profile over the high-loss bottom, (c) the downward refracting profile over the low-loss bottom, and (d) the upward refracting profile over the low-loss bottom. Calculations are shown for two depths: ——— 15 m, and 90 m.

Figure 6 - Vertical coherence of wind noise vs. receiver separation in wavelengths (D/λ) referred to a receiver at two depths: ——— 15 m, and 90 m. The calculations shown were made for the downward refracting sound-speed profile over the high-loss bottom.

7(a)

7(b)

Figure 7 - The noise gain of an unshaded horizontal array with half-wavelength spacing vs. number of elements. The downward refracting profile is shown in (a), the upward refracting profile in (b). Shown are: array over high-loss bottom at 15 m depth \circ , and at 90 m depth Δ ; array over low-loss bottom at 15 m depth \square , and at 90 m depth ∇ .

8(a)

8(c)

8(b)

Figure 8 - Relative signal-to-noise ratio vs. depth for the isovelocity profile (a), the downward refracting profile (b), and the upward refracting profile (c), over both bottom types. Bottom type 1 is the high-loss bottom (silt); 2 is the low-loss bottom (fine sand).